

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion criteria.

Code	Inclusion Criteria	Code	Exclusion Criteria
IC1	Studies whose thematic focus is related to social debt in software development teams.	EC1	Exclude gray literature and duplicate papers.
IC2	Research published in English.	EC2	For studies published from the same project, the one with the greatest contribution will be considered.
IC3	Studies published in indexed journals, scientific dissemination events, conference proceedings, as well as those subjected to peer review.	EC3	Papers that do not address or respond to the aspects or characteristics of social debt described in the formulated research questions, such as (causes, effects, patterns, tools, metrics, and processes, among others), will be excluded.
IC4	Include recent studies whose thematic focus is social debt in the context of software development and whose information is as up-to-date as possible.	EC4	Exclude papers that address the topic of social debt in software development in a superficial manner.
IC5	Include studies or research that describe the methodology in a sequential, solid manner, supported by clear and comprehensible arguments.	EC5	Exclude papers that are not easily accessible, whether due to access restrictions, lack of availability, or any other factor preventing access to the content of the documents.